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As the title of the journal suggests, it is open to all areas of research in endocrinology, both experimental (animal and human) and clinical.

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The journal strives for excellence. It depends on the quality of the manuscripts received. All readers are requested to submit high quality papers to the journal.

We hope that African Journal of Endocrinology will be attractive to its readers and will serve as a well accepted international forum for scientific exchange in endocrinology and metabolism.

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AFRICAN JOURNAL OF ENDOCRINOLOGY

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ANTICARDIOLIPIN ANTIBODIES AND INFERTILITY: THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE.

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ABSTRACT

Background: It is estimated that 10-20 % of couples attending fertility clinics have unexplained infertility. The investigations of causes of infertility and fetal loss are beginning to deal increasingly with immunological factors, and in particular, with the autoimmunity.

Objectives: The aim of the study is to evaluate the prevalence of anticardiolipin antibodies (ACA) in Lagos.

Patients and Methods: Our investigation included 600 patients of the Prenatal Diagnosis & Therapy Centre, College of Medicine of the University of Lagos. The patients included 413 (68.8%) females and 187 (31.2%) males. ACA were analyzed in sera using a commercial ELISA (enzyme - linked immunosorbent assay) test with cardiolipin alone as antigen. Anticardiolipin antibody concentrations were determined using a standard curve based on a series with known concentrations of antibodies and expressed in GPL units.

Result: Five hundred and sixty eight (568) patients (94.7%) tested positive for ACA while only 32 (5.3 %) tested negative. One hundred and seventy nine (179) patients (95.7%) out of 187 males and 389 (94.2%) out of 413 females tested positive for ACA. There was however no statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) relationship between age of respondents and the ACA IgG assay levels; and between sex and ACA IgG assay levels.

Conclusion: There was a high prevalence of ACA in both sexes which may negatively affect conception and pregnancy outcome.

INTRODUCTION

Antiphospholipid (APL) antibodies are a heterogeneous family of autoimmune and alloimmune immunoglobulins, directed predominantly against protein phospholipid complexes (1,2). APL antibodies include lupus anticoagulant (LA), which prolongs phospholipid dependent coagulation *in vitro* and anticardiolipin antibodies (ACA) detected, by solid phase immunoassay. Antiphospholipid syndrome (APS) is a major reproductive complication in women, which is characterized by recurrent foetal loss, thrombosis, and thrombocytopenia in association with ACA. Patients with unexplained infertility often demonstrate many factors, which include the presence of autoantibodies in blood (12). McIntyre (13) reported that APL antibodies interferes in early pregnancy, at the implantation stage by impeding normal reproductive events. The implantation failure may be related to pathological mechanism causing abortion, which is commonly diagnosed as infertility (14). There is clear documentation that ACA are involved in foetal wastages and abortion,

irrespective of the patient having autoimmune disease or not. ACA detection may be the most sensitive method in prevention of foetal wastage (15, 16). ACA have been detected in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus and other autoimmune diseases, infections, drug-induced conditions, and in approximately 10% of the healthy population without predisposing factors (5, 6). ACA have been found in 22% of patients with solid malignancies who also suffered from an increased risk of malignancy associated thrombosis (7). The purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of ACA in patients with unexplained infertility in Lagos, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our investigation included 600 patients of the Prenatal Diagnosis & Therapy Centre, College of Medicine of the University of Lagos. The mean age and age range of the male patients were 40.5 ± 3.6 and 32-48 years, respectively while those of the females were 38.4 ± 5.2 and 28 - 45 years, respectively. Four hundred thirteen (413) (68.8%) of the patients were females, while 187 (31.2%) were

males. ACA were analyzed in sera using a commercial ELISA test with cardiolipin alone as antigen. Concentrations of ACA were determined using a standard curve based on a series with known concentrations of antibodies and expressed in GPL units.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Percentage calculation was carried out. Two-tailed t-test was performed and the significance of p value determination was set at $p < 0.05$.

TABLE 1: The number and percentage of patients that tested positive anticardiolipin antibodies (ACA)

Sex	Positive		Negative	
	n	%	n	%
Male	179	95.7	8	4.3
Female	389	94.2	24	5.8

RESULTS

Five hundred and sixty-eight (568) patients (94.7%) tested positive for ACA, while only 32 (5.3%) tested negative. One hundred and seventy-nine (179) (95.7%) out of 187 males and 389 (94.2%) out of 413 females tested positive for ACA (Table 1). There was however no statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) relationship between age of respondents and the ACA IgG assay levels; and between sex and ACA IgG assay levels.

DISCUSSION

Close to Ninety-five percent (94.7%) of the population studied tested positive for ACA, showing a high prevalence of ACA antibodies in patients with unexplained infertility in Lagos, Nigeria. There was, however, no statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) relationship between the age of respondents and the ACA IgG levels; and between sex and ACA IgG levels. APS is a major reproductive complication in women, which is characterized by recurrent foetal loss, thrombosis, and thrombocytopenia in association with ACA. Patients with unexplained infertility often demonstrate many factors, which include the presence of autoantibodies in blood (12). McIntyre (13) reported that antiphospholipid antibodies interfere in early pregnancy, at the implantation stage by impeding normal reproductive event. There is clear documentation that ACA are

involved in fetal wastages and abortion irrespective of the patient having autoimmune disease or not. In conclusion, there was a high prevalence of ACA in both sexes which may negatively affect conception and pregnancy outcome.

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